

List of Projects & Audited Sites					
Site Name	Location	Audit Type		System	Year of Audit
Marriott Hotel (3 sites)	Pasay, Manila	Level 3	DEA/ PROJ	Water Cooled Chiller System	2019
Mega World – include uptown mall	Various Sites	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2019
ST Micro Electronics	Calamba	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2019
Sun Power Philippines	Binan Laguna	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2019
Cypress Semiconductor	Calamba Laguna	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2019
Micro Chip Philippines	Cabuyao Laguna	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2019
Century Park Hotel Manila	Manila	Level 3 & 2	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2019
21 Ayala Mall Sites	Various Locations	Level 3&2	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2019
Globe Telecom	Makati	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2019
Uptown Mall BGC	BGC Taguig	Level 3	DEA/ PROJ	Water Cooled Chiller System	2019
Coca-Cola Products Philippines	Sta. Rosa & Cabuyao	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2019
BDO Corporate Center Ortigas	Ortigas	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2019
Analog Device	General Trias/Mandaue Cebu	Level 3/1	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2020
GT Tower Makati	Ayala Avenue, Makati	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2020
Solaire Resorts & Hotel	Pasay	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2020
Shangri-la Hotel BGC	BGC Taguig	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2020
The Enterprise Makati	Makati	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2020
RCBC Makati	Makati	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2020
BPI Buendia	Makati	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2020
IMI Philippines – Integrated Micro Electronics	Binan Laguna	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2020
Robinson Mall	Muntinlupa Alabang	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2020
Cardinal Santos Medical Center	San Juan City	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2021
SM Mall San Fernando	Pampanga	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2021
SM Mall Telebastagan	Pampanga	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2021
SM Center Mall	Las Piñas, Manila	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2021
New Resort World Manila	Pasay	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2021
Western Digital	Binan Laguna	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2021
The Medical City Ortigas	Ortigas	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2021
St. Lukes Medical Center	BGC Taguig	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System & AHUs	2021
Solaire Resort and Casino	Paranaque City	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2021
Sofitel	Pasay City	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2021
Manila Peninsula	Makati City	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2021
OKADA Manila	Pasay	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2021
Manila Hotel	Manila City	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System & Boiler System	2021
Grand Hyatt Hotel	Taguig City	Level 2	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2021
Grand Hyatt Office	Taguig City	Level 2	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2021
First Sumiden Circuits Inc	Binan Laguna	Level 3	DEA/ PROJ	Water Cooled Chiller System & Compressed Air	2021
Dusit Thani	Makati City	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2022
P&G Cabuyao	Cabuyao Laguna	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System & Compressed Air	2022
Amkor Laguna	Binan Laguna	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2022
Paranaque Integrated Terminal	Pasay	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2022
Amkor Sucat Area 4	Paranaque City	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2022
Amkor Sucat Area 5	Paranaque City	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2022

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Shangri-La Hotel	Mactan Cebu	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2022
Fairmont Hotel	Makati	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2022
Clark Mimosa	Clark Pampanga	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2022
Shangri – La Shaw Edsa	Ortigas	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2022
Shangri-La Makati	Makati	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2022
Shangri-La the Fort	Manilla	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2022
ON-SEMI	Carmona Cavite	c	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2022
San Miguel Yamamura Packaging Corporation	Manila	Level 1	WEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2022
Festival Mall	Muntinlupa Alabang	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2020
North Gate PDDC Plant	Muntinlupa Alabang	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System	2020
Republic Cement Iligan	Iligan City Lanao Del Norte	Level 1 & 2	DOE	Energy Sources / Compressed Air	2022
Republic Cement Batangas	Taysan Batangas	Level 1 & 2	DOE	Energy Sources/ Compressed Air	2022
Republic Cement Bulacan	Norzagaray	Level 1 & 2	DOE	Energy Sources/ Compressed Air	2022
Green Hills,	San Juan Metro Manila	Level 3	DEA	Water Cooled Chiller System & AHUs	2022
II-VI PMD Chemical Refinery Plant & Infra-Red Optics	Various Sites – Rosario, Cavite	Level 1 & 2	DEA/ DOE/ PROJ	Energy Sources/ 800kW Solar Power/ Compressed Air/ Boiler/ Power System / Agitating System	2023/2024/2025
II-VI PMD Laser Enterprise Plant	Various Sites – Laguna	Level 1 & 2	DEA/ DOE/ PROJ	Energy Sources/ 700kW Solar Power / Compressed Air / Power System/ WWTP	2023/2024/2025